

The Mass Incarceration of African-Americans: Understanding the connection between the Prison Industrial Complex and Slavery

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Abstract

This paper contributes to the burgeoning literature regarding the prison industrial complex. In particular, this study argues that the prison industrial complex is a new form of slavery that relies on the mass incarceration of African-Americans for cheap labor. The overall design of this study is qualitative in nature; utilizing a descriptive case study approach. Three sub-questions were proposed in order to answer the central question at hand. First, the research revealed four precursors of the prison industrial complex; and then the paper examined the racial elements that are pervasive throughout the system. Finally, the research examined the synergies that worked together to create and profit from the prison industrial complex. The results revealed that the prison industrial complex retained the same social iniquities of the four institutions that preceded it. This connection explains the subtle and insidious way that the mass incarceration, particularly of African Americans, is a new form of slavery that exploits black labor.

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Chapter 1: Introduction

Introduction

Criminal Justice is essentially a method of attaining social order by punishing individuals for wrongs that were committed. This method of “social order” is an effort to inhibit additional crimes as well as rehabilitate offenders. The United States incarcerates more individuals than any other country in the world. According to the Pew Trust’s study, *Public Safety, Public Spending: Forecasting America’s Prison Population 2007-2011*, The U.S. prison population saw a 700 percent increase between 1970 and 2005 with a total of 2.2 million people incarcerated. Of the 2.2 million, approximately 900,000 are African-Americans. In other words, in a country where African-Americans make up 13.1% of the population, they account for 40% of the prison population. With the rise of the correctional population; local, state and federal authorities turned to private corporations to handle the influx of inmates. As Marion (2009) explains, “First, a state or locality, either by statute or decree, approves a new prison or solicits bids from private prison companies. Once a prison company secures a contract, it builds the type of correctional facility requested and operates it for the government” (p. 214). With the advent of private prisons; the supposed rehabilitative efforts of the criminal justice system have been exchanged in favor of the profits produced from inmate labor; appropriately titled the prison industrial complex. With this in mind, the prison industrial complex provides a link between the incarceration rates among African-Americans and the history of slavery. This connection explains the subtle and insidious way that the mass incarceration, particularly of African Americans, is a paradigm for the exploitation of black labor comparative to; nevertheless, different from antebellum slavery (1619–1865).

Background of the Topic

To understand the connection between the prison industrial complex and slavery, consider the purveyor: politicians. Politicians were responsible for adding certain provisions regarding slavery into The Constitution of the United States; specifically Section 9 of Article I, “The Migration or Importation of such Persons as any of the States now existing shall think proper to admit, shall not be prohibited by the Congress prior to the Year one thousand eight hundred and eight, but a Tax or duty may be imposed on such Importation, not exceeding ten dollars for each Person.” As Brace (2004) notes, “The presumption of freedom arose from being white and ‘whiteness became a shield from slavery, a highly volatile and unstable form of property” (p. 7). Although slavery was outlawed with the 13th Amendment to the Constitution of the United States, it was not without crafty political wording. The 13th Amendment states, “Neither slavery nor involuntary servitude, except as a punishment for crime whereof the party shall have been duly convicted, shall exist within the United States, or any place subject to their jurisdiction.” In other words, slavery in and of itself is outlawed; however, the use of unpaid labor is fine in the context of the offender being convicted of a punishable crime. Thus, the 13th Amendment to the Constitution of the United States provides the bridge between prison labor and slavery. Prison labor is seen as a profitable business because it “is generally exempt from basic labor protections—like worker’s compensation, labor and industries safeguards, benefits of any kind, or the ability to unionize” (Herival 2007). The post-emancipation period of the United States reveals the utilization of unpaid labor—principally of African-Americans—through various social controls such as convict leasing, black codes, Jim Crow racial segregation, ghettos, hyper-ghettos and prisons. Today, the exploitation of black labor under the prison industrial complex is employed through the use of mandatory sentencing guidelines, and harsher penalties for non-violent offenses.

Statement of Problem

This paper will answer the central question: “Is the prison industrial complex a new form of modern day slavery that unjustly incarcerates African Americans for cheap labor?” To answer this question in an efficient manner, I have assembled three sub-questions: What were the precursors of the prison industrial complex? What are the racial elements within the prison industrial complex? Who benefits from the prison industrial complex?

Professional Significance

This particular project resonates with me for two reasons: (1) As an African-American male, I’ve seen countless family members and friends fall victim to the prison industrial complex; and (2) I feel that it is necessary to educate others in order to create an honest discussion about this topic. The Constitution of the United States, the supreme law of the land, was drafted with several provisions that included slavery. Thus, racial inequality was formed as the very fabric of American society. For centuries, African-Americans were subjected to inconceivable treatment: Black codes, Jim Crow racial segregation, COINTELPRO, and much more. Although critics may argue that America is now a post racial society—especially in the age of President Barack Obama—I would argue that America has continued its subjugation of African Americans through the use of the prison industrial complex.

Overview of Methodology

A triangulation of data will be collected including documents, interviews, artifacts, and historical archives. Specifically, I will review Bureau of Justice Statistics, FBI UCR statistics, and scholarly articles to provide a modern source of data relative to this topic. Furthermore, The Constitution of the United States, The Emancipation Proclamation, and laws primarily enacted during the Reconstruction Period (1865-1877) will be analyzed to gain a historical context of the issue. A careful analysis of the data will shed light on the following questions: What were the

precursors of the prison industrial complex? What are the racial elements within the prison industrial complex? Who benefits from the prison industrial complex?

Delimitations

The focus of this study is not an attempt to demonize anyone with regard to race or ethnicity. Rather, the purpose is to highlight the correlation between slavery, and the disparate treatment of African Americans in terms of prison sentencing and convictions. Because this paper relies on historical interpretations, primary data collection falls outside of the parameters of the investigation. The secondary findings; however, shall provide the reader with the opportunity to make an informed decision with respect to the prison industrial complex as a new form of slavery.

Definition of Terms

- **Prison industrial complex:** A term derived from the military industrial complex; it explains the mass incarceration and expansion of prisons in the United States because of the political influence that private prison corporations wield.
- **Bureau of Justice Statistics:** A federal government agency that collects information regarding crime in America.
- **Statute/Decree:** Legislation that is enacted to proclaim or prohibit certain actions.
- **Convict leasing:** A system enacted during the Reconstruction period where blacks were convicted of petty offenses and then leased out to private parties to provide free labor.
- **Black codes:** A set of post-emancipation laws that were enacted which prohibited freed Africa-Americans from certain activities. The laws guaranteed that blacks would still be victims of involuntary servitude.

- **Jim Crow racial segregation:** laws enacted by former Confederate states that created racial segregation under the guise of “separate but equal” societies and facilities.
- **COINTELPRO:** A covert FBI operation that was responsible for infiltrating, disrupting, and discrediting, major black leaders and organizations.
- **FBI’s Uniform Crime Report:** Crime statistics collected and published by the FBI.

Summary

The main objective of this paper is to provide a thorough answer as to whether there is a correlation between slavery and the prison industrial complex. Slavery was a particularly brutal form of involuntary servitude where African-Americans labored for virtually nothing. The result of slavery was pure profits for the entities involved. Conversely, the prison industrial complex exists with the knowledge that racial inequalities are present in the arrest, sentencing, and convictions of African-Americans. Under those circumstances, politicians have essentially placed re-election prospects and greed above rehabilitating the correctional population. Now, prisoners—which are disproportionately African-American—are laboring under the same conditions of slavery for corporations that are profiting from this cheap labor.

Chapter 2: Literature Review

Part I: Literature Review

The purpose of this chapter is to evaluate the available literature to gain a better understanding on the connection between antebellum slavery (1619–1865) and the prison industrial complex (state slavery). A careful analysis of the data will shed light on the following questions: What were the precursors of the prison industrial complex? What are the racial elements within the prison industrial complex? Who benefits from the prison industrial complex? More importantly, this review will synthesize ideas to address the main point: The prison industrial complex is a new form of modern day slavery that unjustly incarcerates African-Americans for cheap labor.

Sub-Question 1: What were the precursors of the prison industrial complex?

With respect to the prison industrial complex, it appears that there are a number of precursors that led to this system. Wacquant (2002) conducted a study that revealed four distinct institutions that are recognized as antecedents, and primarily used to control African-Americans (p. 41). These four institutions include: chattel slavery, Jim Crow segregation, the ghetto, and hyper-ghettos (Wacquant, 2002, p. 41). As noted by Wacquant in Table 1 below, chattel slavery is the progenitor where the form of labor is “unfree” and fixed; the plantation is the core of the economy while the slave is the dominant social type. Moreover, the dismantling of slavery led to Jim Crow where the labor is free and fixed; the core of the economy is agrarian and extractive, and the dominant social type is the slave (Wacquant, 2002, p. 42). Simultaneously, the ghetto provided free mobile labor with segmented industrial manufacturing as the center of the economy where blacks were menial workers. Lastly, hyper-ghettos provided fixed surplus labor using polarized postindustrial services, and blacks as welfare recipients & criminals (Wacquant, 2002, p. 42). Thus, each system is similar to the prison industrial complex in that it is used to

extract labor while ostracizing African-Americans. Although the dynamics have changed over time, this study illuminates the unique socioeconomic situation affecting African-Americans today. Essentially, the research provides the foundation that is necessary in conveying the connection between slavery and the prison industrial complex.

TABLE I *The four 'peculiar institutions' and their basis*

Institution	Form of labour	Core of economy	Dominant social type
Slavery (1619–1865)	unfree fixed labour	Plantation	slave
Jim Crow (South, 1865–1965)	free fixed labour	Agrarian and extractive	sharecropper
Ghetto (North, 1915–68)	free mobile labour	Segmented industrial manufacturing	menial worker
Hyperghetto & Prison (1968–)	fixed surplus labour	Polarized postindustrial services	welfare recipient & criminal

Sub-Question 2: What are the racial elements of the prison industrial complex?

By many accounts, the prison industrial complex is comprised of numerous racial elements. Alexander (2011) examined the comparable data between slavery, Jim Crow and the prison industrial complex and found that there are more African-Americans under correctional supervision than were enslaved in 1850 (p.9). She also found that “In 2007 more black men were disenfranchised than in 1870, the year the Fifteenth Amendment was ratified prohibiting laws that explicitly deny the right to vote on the basis of race” (Alexander, 2011, p. 9). According to Alexander, not everyone has been subjected to mass incarceration, “the overwhelming majority of the increase in imprisonment has been poor people of color, with the most astonishing rates of incarceration found among black men” (p. 12). Alexander demonstrates that the war on drugs, not crime rates, accounts for the mass incarceration of African-Americans today (p. 12). Additionally, she found that immediately following the Anti-Drug Abuse Act of 1986, which established mandatory minimum sentences, drug convictions increased 1000%; “an increase that

bears no relationship to patterns of drug use or sales” (Alexander, p. 12). Other studies back Alexander’s findings that racial disparities exist within the prison industrial complex. For example, according to a 2006 study by the ACLU entitled *Cracks in the System: Twenty Years of the Unjust Federal Crack Cocaine Law*, “Recent data indicates that African Americans make up 15% of the country’s drug users, yet they comprise 37% of those arrested for drug violations, 59% of those convicted, and 74% of those sentenced to prison for a drug offense (p. I). As noted in Table 2 below, more than 80% of the defendants sentenced for crack offenses are African American, despite the fact that more than 66% of crack users are white or Hispanic” (Vagins et al. 2006, p. 1). Thus, the studies reveal that the war on drugs disproportionately affects African-Americans much like chattel slavery.

TABLE 2 In 2003, whites constituted 7.8% and African Americans constituted more than 80% of the defendants sentenced under the harsh federal crack cocaine laws, despite the fact that more than 66% of crack cocaine users in the United States are white or Hispanic.

2003 Federal Crack Cocaine Defendants

Source: U.S. SENTENCING COMMISSION, 2003 SOURCEBOOK OF FEDERAL SENTENCING, Table 34 (2003), available at <http://www.uscc.gov/ANNRPT/2003/table34.pdf>.

Crack Cocaine Users

Source: SUBSTANCE ABUSE AND MENTAL HEALTH SERVICES ADMINISTRATION, 2004 NATIONAL SURVEY ON DRUG USE AND HEALTH, POPULATION ESTIMATES 1995, Table 1.43a (2005), available at <http://www.oas.samhsa.gov/Nhsda/2k3tabs/Sect1peTabs1to66.htm#tab1.43a>.

Sentencing disparities also disproportionately affect African-Americans more than any other race. As Vagins et al. (2006) has found, “The average sentence for a crack cocaine offense in 2003, which was 123 months, was 3.5 years longer than the average sentence of 81 months for an offense involving the powder form of the drug. African-Americans now serve virtually as

much time in prison for a drug offense at 58.7 months, as whites do for a violent offense at 61.7 months” As Muster (2001) maintains, “disparities are primarily generated by departures from the guidelines, rather than differential sentencing within the guidelines. Departures produce about 55 percent of the black-white difference and 70 percent of the male-female difference. Although black-white disparities occur across offenses, the largest differences are for drug trafficking” (p. 285). The literature shows that jurisprudence clearly accounts for many racial elements that are persistent throughout the prison industrial complex.

Another racial aspect of the prison industrial complex is the school-to-prison pipeline. As Losen et al. (2003) notes, school policies have changed to include zero-tolerance for school violations and mandatory referrals to law enforcement authorities (p. 10). The research suggests that “Black students are 2.6 times as likely to be suspended as white students. In 2000, they represented 17 percent of the student population but 34 percent of those suspended. Between 1972 and 2000, the percentage of white students suspended annually for more than one day rose from 3.1 percent to 5.09 percent. Yet, during the same period, the percentage for black students rose from 6 percent to 13.2 percent” (Losen et al. 2003, p. 10). Another study conducted by the Education Department’s Office for Civil Rights entitled *Civil Rights Data Collection*, advises that 35% of in school-related arrests, and 42% of law enforcement referrals are African-American students (p. 2). Figure 1, below is a snapshot of the aforementioned study illustrating the disparity in school discipline for African-Americans.

Figure 1

Highlighting the complex racial elements relative to the prison industrial complex is necessary to frame the context of this study. That is, there are clear disparities that exist within the prison industrial complex; however, this research interprets and explains that it is uniquely because the system is a new form of slavery meant to extract cheap labor from African-Americans.

Sub-Question 3: Who benefits from the prison industrial complex?

The mass incarceration boom from the 1980s to present created a market for businesses to benefit financially. As Friedmann (2012) explains, local, state, and federal authorities created a multi-billion dollar industry when they decided to contract with private prison corporations to exploit crime and punishment (p. 20). Notable examples of private prison corporations are Corrections Corporation of America (CCA), GEO Group, Management and Training Corp. (MTC), and Cornell Corrections (Friedmann 2012, p. 20). Friedmann found that “CCA alone grossed \$1.67 billion in revenue in 2010; its closest competitor, GEO Group, grossed \$1.24 billion” (p. 20). Private prisons make money by contracting inmate labor out to private

corporations in exchange for money (Freidmann 2012, p. 20). Prison labor is seen as a profitable business because it “is generally exempt from basic labor protections—like worker’s compensation, labor and industries safeguards, benefits of any kind, or the ability to unionize” (Herival & Wright, 2007, p. xvi). A study conducted by Pelaez (2008) revealed that 37 states have legalized the hiring out of prisons to private corporations. Furthermore, the list of corporations include: IBM, Boeing, Motorola, Microsoft, AT&T, Wireless, Texas Instrument, Dell, Compaq, Honeywell, Hewlett-Packard, Nortel, Lucent Technologies, 3Com, Intel, Northern Telecom, TWA, Nordstrom’s, Revlon, Macy’s, Pierre Cardin, Target Stores, and more” (Pelaez 2008). In prison, inmates are paid anywhere between 17 and 50 cents per hour for what’s considered highly skilled work (Pelaez 2008).

The research clearly indicates that there are several entities that directly benefit from the prison industrial complex. By detailing the synergies involved in this system, my attempt is to conceptualize the motive, and create an honest discussion regarding its ethical proportions. Principally, this study contributes to the idea that the prison industrial complex is a paradigm for the exploitation of black labor comparative to; nevertheless, different from antebellum slavery.

Figure 2

Summary

The prison industrial complex is a new form of modern day slavery that unjustly incarcerates African Americans for cheap labor. The precursors to the prison industrial complex helped establish a framework for extracting labor from blacks while socially ostracizing them in the process. Studies have shown that the war on drugs, not violence, mainly contributed to racial disparities in the mass incarceration of African-Americans. In addition, draconian sentencing laws and the school-to-prison pipeline are other disturbing racial elements that permeate the prison industrial complex. Evident are the parallel elements of disenfranchisement, racial disparity, and uneven discipline found in the institutions of slavery, Jim Crow, the ghettos and the prison industrial complex.

Chapter 3: Research Design and Methodology

Introduction

This paper is guided by the central question: “Is the prison industrial complex a new form of modern day slavery that unjustly incarcerates African-Americans for cheap labor?” The overall design of this project will be qualitative in nature to test the following sub-questions: What were the precursors of the prison industrial complex? What are the racial elements within the prison industrial complex? Who benefits from the prison industrial complex? The type of qualitative investigation that I will pursue is a descriptive case study. As Yin (2002) notes, “the case studies unique strength is its ability to deal with a full variety of evidence—documents, artifacts, interviews, and observations—beyond what might be available in conventional historical study” (p. 8). Specifically, the need for the case study method is the desire to explain the complex connection between slavery and the prison industrial complex.

Plan of action

A triangulation of data will be collected including documents, surveys, artifacts, and historical archives in interpretation of this phenomenon. In essence, this paper will explore a sensitive issue to not only verify existing theories, but to also gain a new perspective on this topic. Moreover, this paper will provide the reader with the necessary information to make an informed decision with respect to the prison industrial complex as a new form of slavery.

Research Methodology for Data Collection

The first sub-question lays the groundwork for the study: “What were the precursors of the prison industrial complex?” The literature suggests that there are four distinct institutions that were the root causes of the prison industrial complex. Documents such as The Constitution of the United States, The Emancipation Proclamation, and “black codes” enacted during the Reconstruction Period (1865-1877) will be analyzed to provide a historical context for these institutions. In addition, the research will synthesize information from the Bureau of Justice Statistics, FBI UCR statistics, and scholarly articles to illuminate the correlation between the four institutions and the prison industrial complex.

The second sub-question asks: “What are the racial elements within the prison industrial complex?” This paper will attempt to answer this question by identifying the key elements that contribute to the disproportionate incarceration of African-Americans. Supporting documentation will include racial data concerning the War on Drugs and its associated laws, arrests, U.S Sentencing guidelines, and zero-tolerance school policies. The findings will elucidate the many layers of racial elements pervasive throughout the prison industrial complex and reveal the patterns in relation to Jim Crow and slavery.

The third and final sub-question asks: Who benefits from the prison industrial complex? To address this question, the research will focus on the synergies that worked together to create

the prison industrial complex; how it was created; the reasoning for doing so; and the profit margins associated with the system. Further, I intend to detail how the system maintains some elements of slavery as a means to extract free labor, specifically from African-Americans. Annual reports of private prison corporations will be analyzed to detail each company's mission and goals. I will also examine articles and studies from experts that explain how corporations are entrenched in the prison industrial complex. Moreover, the research will show that the prison industrial complex is a calculated system where the core of the economy is polarized post industrial services, the dominant social type is mainly the black criminal, and the form of labor is fixed surplus. Principally, this study contributes to the idea that the prison industrial complex is a paradigm for the exploitation of black labor comparative to; nevertheless, distinct from slavery.

Organization and Analysis of Data

The organization and analysis of the collected data will be arranged using an iterative process. In particular, the information will be organized according to the sub-questions proposed, and then examined to see if the findings fit into the larger discussion of the prison industrial complex as a new form of slavery. Ultimately, the goal is to develop a case description that answers the papers central question using qualitative content analysis. According to Babbie (2001), content analysis is "a coding operation with coding being the process of transforming raw data into a standardized form" (p.309). Figure 3 below details the basic proceeding of qualitative content analysis (Glaser & Laudel, 1999, p.4).

Figure 3

Qualitative content analysis was selected because of “its rule-based logic and methodologically controlled step-by-step procedures of analysis” (Kohlbacher, 2006). Essentially, my sub-question will be presented, the information will be analyzed, and finally the data will be interpreted. Overall, the qualitative content analysis will attempt to answer the question: Is the prison industrial complex a new form of modern day slavery that unjustly incarcerates African-Americans for cheap labor?

Chapter 4: Results of the Study

Introduction

As stated in Chapter 1, the study examined the central question: “Is the prison industrial complex a new form of modern day slavery that unjustly incarcerates African-Americans for cheap labor?” The study explored this phenomenon through the proposition of three sub-questions: What were the precursors to the prison industrial complex? What are the racial elements within the prison industrial complex? Who benefits from the prison industrial complex? This chapter will attempt to answer the central question through the summarization of each sub-question.

Sub-Question 1: What were the precursors of the prison industrial complex?

To answer sub-question one; this paper will review the four precursors of the prison industrial complex as noted by Wacquant (2002) in Chapter 2. This sub-question attempts to establish the root causes of the prison industrial complex, and provide a framework for answering the central question.

Slavery

According to Higginbotham (1980), the foundation of slavery was gradually laid in the legal system of the United States (p. 27). He contends that social biases translated into harsh punitive judgments to perpetuate brutal behavior against blacks (p.28). Higginbotham highlights the 1640 Virginia legal case *Re Negro Punch* as the precedent for partiality in dealing with blacks:

Three runaway servants, two white and one black (John Punch), were captured in Maryland and each sentenced to be whipped; but the judicial parity stopped with the whipping. The court then imposed the following sentences for the white runaways: one year of indentured service with their master, and three years apiece of indentured service to the colony. John Punch—the black runaway—was ordered by the court to serve his master for the rest of his life. (p. 28)

Slavery as a legal institution was initially recognized by the colony of Massachusetts in its 1641 Body of Liberties: “There shall never be any bond slavery or captivity among us unless it be lawful captives taken in just wars, and such strangers as willingly sell themselves or are sold to us” (Art. 91). However, Higginbotham notes that Virginia took the lead in turning slavery into a “legal dogma.” (p. 58) He explains that the Virginia General Assembly declaration of 1705 Chapter XLIX specifically declared all servants who were not Christians in their native country as slaves and property of their master (p. 53). In addition to the slave codes that were pervasive throughout much of the antebellum south, the Constitution of the United States included three specific clauses that allowed the institution of slavery. Article 1, Section 2, Clause 3 apportioned

taxes and Congressional representation in accordance with the population; however, it also deemed slaves as three-fifths of a person as a mechanism to count slaves without giving them the right to vote. Article 4, Section 2, Clause 3 required escaped slaves to be brought back to their masters. This particular clause was later nullified by the 13th Amendment to the Constitution of the United States. Finally, Article 1, Section 9, Clause 1 strictly barred any attempt to outlaw the importation of slaves before 1808; however, slavery continued as an institution for approximately 60 years after 1808. A study by Wacquant (2002) notes “in the Americas property-in-person was geared primarily to the provision and control of labor” (p. 44-45). As Smith (1998) explains, “the growing reliance on profitable staple crops such as tobacco, rice, and indigo served to inspire and subsequently entrench race-based slavery, especially in the colonial South” (p. 3).

Jim Crow

On January 1, 1863 President Abraham Lincoln issued the Emancipation Proclamation declaring that “all persons held as slaves within said designated States, and parts of States, are, and henceforward shall be free” (National Archives and Records Administration, 2010). Although Lincoln had good intentions with the Emancipation Proclamation, a study by Vorenberg (2001) reveals that it was the Union’s victory in the American Civil War along with the 13th Amendment that effectively ended slavery (p. 2). The 13th Amendment states, “Neither slavery nor involuntary servitude, except as a punishment for crime whereof the party shall have been duly convicted, shall exist within the United States, or any place subject to their jurisdiction” (National Archives and Records Administration, 2010). Wacquant (2002) reveals that the post-emancipation period of the United States “created a double dilemma for Southern white society: how to secure anew the labor of former slaves, without whom the region’s

economy would collapse, and how to sustain the cardinal, status distinction between whites and persons of color” (p. 45-46).

While the 13th Amendment to the Constitution ended slavery, it also provided a legal mechanism for southern states to extract labor from blacks. As previously noted, the 13th Amendment prohibited slavery and involuntary servitude except as punishment for a crime. The former slave states used the 13th Amendment to facilitate a change in the social status between whites and blacks, and to regulate black labor. Wacquant (2002) explains that the first solution was a separation of whites and blacks through racial segregation (p. 45). He states that “the religious and pseudo-scientific belief in racial difference reconciled the brute fact of un-free labor with the doctrine of liberty premised on natural rights by reducing the slave to live property—three-fifths of a man according to the sacred scriptures of the Constitution” (p. 45). The second solution that southern states prescribed was the enactment of “black codes” that made it easier to force blacks into peonage by convicting them of petty crimes (Dickerson, 2003, p. 43). As a result of black codes, a convict leasing system was created “to allow white slave plantation owners in the South to literally purchase prisoners to live on their property and work under their control” (Browne, 2007, p. 43). Chain gangs were also used by white southerners to regulate black labor. With respect to chain gangs, “chains were wrapped around the ankles of prisoners, shackling five together while they worked, ate, and slept” (Browne 2007, p. 43).

Ghettos

With industrial manufacturing on the rise, African Americans migrated en masse to the booming labor markets in the Northeastern part of America. A study by Massey (1993) found that racial segregation in the north was just as bad for blacks as it was in the south. In particular, Massey explains that white fear, and housing segregation trapped blacks from all socioeconomic classes in the ghetto (p. 36-40). According to Massey, in 1921 the National Association of Real

Estate Brokers stated that “a Realtor should never be instrumental in introducing into a neighborhood...members of any race or nationality...whose presence will clearly be detrimental to property values in that neighborhood” (p. 37). Massey’s study reveals that the National Association of Real Estate Brokers maintained this policy until 1950 (p. 37). Furthermore, Massey notes that blacks would often face violence from white mobs that were bent on ensuring that their neighborhoods remained all white (p. 37). He states that Realtors preyed on the fact that blacks did not have many housing options. For example, Massey reveals that Realtors used various methods to give the impression of opening up neighborhoods to blacks while extracting profits (p. 37). Massey explains that Realtors would find a white area that was adjacent to the ghetto, quietly buy real estate in the white area, and sell to blacks to stoke racial fears. After selling homes to black residents, Realtors would engage in what’s called “block-busting”—going door-to-door to whites in the neighborhood warning them of an invasion of black residents. As a result, whites would sell their homes well below market value to these same Realtors. Next, the Realtors would sell the homes to blacks at much higher prices than whites paid, allowing Realtors to reap substantial profits (p. 38). As Massey notes, “The prevalence of these quick-profit schemes meant that the ghetto constantly followed the black middle class as it sought to escape from the poverty, blight, and misery of the black slum” (p. 39).

Massey explains that extensive black migration to large urban areas caused whites to flee in mass to suburban areas (p. 39-45). He contends that this sudden change in housing patterns between whites and blacks “led to an unprecedented increase in the physical size of the ghetto during the 1950s and 1960s” (p. 45). Massey’s study also highlights the practice of “redlining”—a system developed by the federal government’s Home Owners’ Loan Corporation (HOLC) that relied on neighborhood ratings to deny blacks home loans (p. 51). Wacquant (2002) notes that

during this time period “the ‘job ceiling’ restricted [blacks] to the most hazardous, menial, and underpaid occupations in both industry and personal services” (p. 47). He further asserts that the civil rights legislation during the 1960s forced whites to accept integration in principle, while supporting laws meant to suppress black progress (p. 49). Wacquant brilliantly sums up the ghetto as “an ethno racial prison: it engages a dishonored category and severely curtails the life chances of its members in support of the ‘monopolization of ideal and material goods or opportunities’ by the dominant status group dwelling on its outskirts” (p. 51).

Hyper-ghettos & Prisons

While the civil rights act of the 1960s banned housing discrimination in the U.S, Massey (1993) notes that racial segregation remained a reality for many blacks; particularly those who were stuck in the ghetto (p. 61). This further isolation of blacks led to highly impoverished crime ridden areas known as hyper-ghettos. Wacquant (2002) notes that when the hyper-ghettos expanded throughout the Northern and Southern parts of the U.S. so too did the carceral policies (p. 52). He notes that the adjoining of the hyper-ghetto with the carceral institution was an effort to “remold the social meaning and significance of ‘race’ in accordance with the dictates of the deregulated economy and the post-Keynesian state” (p. 55). Wacquant argues that black has now become synonymous with criminal in today’s age (p.56). He summarizes his study by tying together slavery and the prison industrial complex:

It is not only the pre-eminent institution for signifying and enforcing blackness, much as slavery was during the first three centuries of US history....mass incarceration also induces the civic death of those it ensnares by extruding them from the social compact. (p. 57)

Thus, the findings prove that there is a connection between the prison industrial complex and slavery. In particular, the research reveals that Jim Crow segregation, the ghetto, and hyper-ghettos maintained key dynamics of slavery—racial discrimination and bondage along with the regulation of black labor. These components now exist within the institution known as the prison

industrial complex—a method of mass incarceration primarily used to exploit cheap labor. This information is consistent with this paper’s position that the prison industrial complex is a new form of modern day slavery that unjustly incarcerates African Americans for cheap labor.

Sub-Question 2: What are the racial elements within the prison industrial complex?

This section will review relevant data to crystallize the racial elements within the prison industrial complex. The objective of this piece is to highlight the disproportionate treatment that African-Americans face with respect to the “War on Drugs” and its associated laws, arrests, U.S Sentencing guidelines, and zero-tolerance school policies. The findings will elucidate the connection between slavery and the prison industrial complex, and provide a framework for answering the central question.

Mass incarceration is a key element of the prison industrial complex, and the following is the result of this component relative to blacks. As previously noted by Alexander (2011), the mass incarceration of African-Americans is primarily because of the War on Drugs (p. 12). In particular, there are two key laws of interest: The Anti-Drug Abuse Act of 1986, and The Anti-Drug Abuse Act of 1988. These two laws, as McCurdy and Vagins (2006) note, established mandatory minimum sentences for various drugs; however, the most infamous part of these laws were the “tougher sentences for crack cocaine offenses than for powder cocaine cases” (p. 1).

Their study reveals the following:

The [1986] Act provided that individuals convicted of crimes involving 500 grams of powder cocaine or just 5 grams of crack (the weight of two pennies) were sentenced to at least 5 years imprisonment, without regard to any mitigating factors. The Act also provided that those individuals convicted of crimes involving 5000 grams of powder cocaine and 50 grams of crack (the weight of a candy bar) be sentenced to 10 years imprisonment. The 1988 Act created a 5-year mandatory minimum and 20-year maximum sentence for simple possession of 5 grams or more of crack cocaine. The maximum penalty for simple possession of any amount of powder cocaine or any other drug remained at no more than 1 year in prison. (p. 2)

A study by Jamie Fellner (2009), entitled “*Race, Drugs, and Law Enforcement in the United States*” delves deeper into the racial elements persistent in drug usage, possession and trafficking. Fellner maintains that the two drug abuse acts of the 1980s came about because “Politicians were able to woo a white electorate anxious about its [supposedly] declining status through the race-coded language of drugs and crime” (p. 264). She maintains that the laws and enforcement mechanisms were more so a way to control minorities rather than respond objectively to criminal danger (p. 265). Fellner uses drug usage rates to defend her position: “Because the white population is more than six times greater than the black population, the absolute number of white drug offenders is far greater than that of black drug offenders” (p. 266). Fellner’s study is backed by data from the National Survey on Drug Use and Health, 2011. Table 3 below details the type of illicit drug and usage rates according to Race/Ethnicity.

National Survey on Drug Use and Health, 2011 (Substance abuse & Mental Health Data Archive)

Table 3

Fellner’s study also details drug trafficking among Race/Ethnicity noting that “although the proportion of sellers was twice that among blacks than among whites, in absolute numbers far more whites (939,345) reported drug selling than blacks (268,170)” (p. 268). Fellner also explains that “in the last six years, the ratio of black to white drug arrest rates has ranged between 3.5 and 3.9” (p. 272). Fellner’s empirical data is consistent with the Bureau of Justice

Statistics as indicated in Table 4 below. For example, of the 225,242 people arrested for drugs 67,271 or 30% were white, 91,775 or 41% were black, and 47,479 or 21% were Hispanic. A 2013 study by the ACLU entitled “*The War on Marijuana in Black and White*” is consistent with Fellner’s findings: “Blacks are 3.73 times more likely than whites to be arrested for Marijuana possession” (p. 17). The ACLU study further explains: “As the overall number of Marijuana arrests has increased over the past decade, the white arrest rate has remained constant at around 192 per 100,000, whereas the Black arrest rate has risen from 537 per 100,000 in 2001 (and 521 per 100,000 in 2002) to 716 per 100,000 in 2010” (p. 20).

Fellner (2009) attributes the difference in drug arrest rates of blacks to whites on “demographics, the extent of community complaints, police allocation of resources, racial profiling, and the relative ease of making drug arrests in minority urban areas compared to white areas” (p. 270). Fellner also highlights a discouraging trend regarding the rates that blacks go to prison for drug offenses relative to whites: “the black rate (256.2 per 100,000 black adults) is ten times greater than the white rate (25.3 per 100,000 white adults)” (p. 275).

TABLE 4
Estimated number of sentenced prisoners under state jurisdiction, by offense, sex, race, and Hispanic origin, December 31, 2011

Offense	All inmates ^a	Male	Female	White ^b	Black ^b	Hispanic
Total	1,341,804	1,250,214	91,590	465,180	509,677	282,353
Violent	710,875	678,786	33,695	228,782	284,631	162,489
Murder ^c	163,762	154,359	9,821	45,369	65,568	37,956
Manslaughter	21,051	18,544	2,587	8,107	7,408	3,456
Rape/sexual assault	165,656	163,863	2,032	79,282	39,975	35,863
Robbery	181,415	173,640	8,177	38,312	99,096	36,694
Aggravated or simple assault	138,574	131,100	7,816	42,375	56,281	38,252
Other violent	40,416	37,281	3,262	15,336	16,304	10,270
Property	245,351	220,753	25,486	108,560	78,197	38,264
Burglary	128,823	122,837	6,298	53,547	46,795	22,038
Larceny-theft	42,029	35,195	7,046	19,617	12,679	5,679
Motor vehicle theft	14,703	13,782	963	6,596	3,330	4,132
Fraud	30,333	22,000	8,559	14,738	8,256	2,628
Other property	29,463	26,940	2,621	14,063	7,137	3,786
Drug ^d	225,242	203,081	22,971	67,271	91,775	47,479
Public order ^e	141,803	134,203	7,954	54,834	50,489	32,275
Other/unspecified ^f	18,534	13,391	1,484	5,733	4,585	1,846

Bureau of Justice Statistics, Federal Justice Statistics Program; Prisoners in 2012 - Advance Counts

Table 4

Another racial element of the prison industrial complex is the sentencing disparity between whites and blacks. A study by David Mustard (2001) entitled “Racial, ethnic, and gender disparities in sentencing: Evidence from The U.S. federal courts,” examined over 77,000 federal offenders sentenced under the Sentencing Reform Act of 1984. According to Mustard, the Sentencing Reform Act of 1984 was “designed to eliminate sentencing disparities and state explicitly that race, gender, ethnicity, and income should not affect the sentence length” (p. 285). However, his study found that disparities are primarily generated when judges depart from the sentencing guidelines (p. 285). Mustard notes that this departure produces approximately “55 percent of the black-white difference” (p. 285). Mustard’s empirical data reveals that “whites receive the lowest average sentence of 32.1 months, Hispanics receive a sentence of 54.1 months, and blacks receive 64.1 months, which are 68.5 percent and 99.6 percent larger than the average sentence for whites” (p. 296). Mustard also found that “Bank robbery and drug trafficking exhibit the largest black-white differential” (p. 304). Moreover, he explains that “the percentage difference is greatest for those convicted of drug trafficking, where blacks are assigned sentences 13.7 percent longer than whites” (p. 304). Finally, Mustard notes that if there is an option of no prison term, whites are far more likely to receive that alternative than blacks (p. 306).

Finally, this paper will outline the findings with respect to the school-to-prison pipeline as a racial element of the prison industrial complex. The school-to-prison pipeline is perhaps the starting point where many African-Americans get swept into the prison industrial complex. As indicated in Table 5 below, schools exist as a breeding ground for the prison industrial complex relative to black and Hispanic kids (See table 5).

(Infographic from www.suspensionstories.com)

Table 5

The findings suggest that blacks and Hispanics are far more likely to be suspended, expelled, involved in in-school arrests, or referred to law enforcement than white students. A study by Wald and Losen (2003) entitled “*Defining and redirecting a school-to-prison pipeline,*” notes that the disparities are likely because of “racial profiling in schools” (p. 13). They explain that in addition to racial profiling, a number of other factors exist: the expansion of zero-tolerance school policies, increased law enforcement presence at schools, and a lack of school resources (p.13). Skiba (2000) explains this phenomenon:

Investigations of student behavior, race, and discipline have found no evidence that African Americans misbehave at a significantly higher rate. If anything, available research suggests that black students tend to receive harsher punishments than white students, and that those harsher consequences may be administered for less severe offenses. In an analysis of the reasons middle school students in one urban district were referred to the office, white students were more often referred for vandalism, smoking, endangerment, obscene language, and drugs and alcohol. In contrast, black students were

more often referred to the school office for loitering, disrespect, excessive noise, threats, and a catch-all category called conduct interference. (p.12)

Based on the foregoing the research indicates that there are numerous racial elements that are pervasive throughout the prison industrial complex. The most severe racial elements are those concerning the war on drugs, arrests, U.S Sentencing guidelines, and zero-tolerance school policies. This paper deduces that these aspects are present specifically because the prison industrial complex maintains components of slavery and its successive institutions—racial segregation, and bondage.

Sub-Question 3: Who benefits from the prison industrial complex?

To answer sub-question 3; the research will focus on the synergies that worked together to create the prison industrial complex; how it was created; the reasoning for doing so; and the profit model associated with the system. This information will provide a framework for answering the central question.

Private prison corporations primarily exist out of the need for local, state, and federal authorities to reduce costs associated with the housing and supervision of inmates. As Marion (2009) explains, political leaders believed that “competition among [different] firms result in better facilities for the inmates as well as lower costs to taxpayers” (p. 217). His study details the process in which local, state, or federal leaders employ private prison corporations:

First, a state or locality, either by statute or decree, approves a new prison or solicits bids from private prison companies. Once a prison company secures a contract, it builds the type of correctional facility requested and operates it for the government. (p. 214)

Marion notes that these private prison corporations are publicly traded and strictly out for profits (p.213). He identifies one such firm, Corrections Corporation of America (CCA), as “the oldest and most well-known private prison company [worth] nearly \$1.5 billion in total revenue” (p. 213). A look at CCA’s 2013 annual report reveals that it is “the nation’s largest owner of

privatized correctional and detention facilities and one of the largest prison operators in the United States behind only the federal government and three states” (p. 5). CCA notes in the risk section of its 2013 annual report that “any changes with respect to drugs and controlled substances or illegal immigration could affect the number of persons arrested, convicted, and sentenced, thereby potentially reducing demand for correctional facilities to house them” (p. 27).

A 2013 study conducted by In the Public Interest entitled “How Lockup Quotas and “Low-Crime Taxes” Guarantee Profits,” detailed the profit models of private prison corporations. Their findings indicate that “65% of private prison contracts include an occupancy guarantee in the form of quotas or required payments for empty prison cells” (p. 2). They note that some states are locked into quotas requiring between 80% to 100% occupancy (p.2). The reasoning, In the Public Interest notes, is so companies can “guarantee profits and reduce their financial risk” (p. 5). In the Public Interest also found that private prison corporations have spent millions lobbying the government for favorable policies that protect their investments. For example, “CCA spent \$17.4 million in lobbying expenditures from 2002 through 2012, and spent \$1.9 million in political contributions from 2003 to 2012 (p. 5). Another study by In the Public Interest (2014) entitled “The Costs of Private Prisons,” notes that private prison corporations employ numerous tools to generate profits: expensive contract terms, and automatic contract price increases (p. 4-5). Ultimately, these methods are used to ensure that private prison corporations reap substantial profits.

With respect to Race/Ethnicity, the research also strongly suggests that private prison corporations are intentionally housing people of color. A 2013 study conducted by Petrella entitled “*The Color of Corporate Corrections, Part II: Contractual Exemptions and the Overrepresentation of People of Color in Private Prisons,*” explains that people of color are

overrepresented in private prisons around the country. Petrella found that private prison corporations have clauses in their contract that often exclude older inmates and those who suffer from health related issues. Petrella's study reveals that private prison corporations use the health and age of the inmate as a proxy for race without specific reference to it. Petrella further elaborates:

The older the prisoner, the more likely that prisoner is to be "Non-Hispanic, white." Correspondingly, the younger the prisoner, the more likely that prisoner is to be a person of color. Most prisoners over 50 today were convicted and sentenced before the operationalization of the so-called "War on Drugs," a skein of policies that have disproportionately criminalized communities of color. By implication, the vast majority of those incarcerated prior to 1980—both in real numbers and on a percentage basis—were "Non-Hispanic, white." Contrastingly, black individuals constituted 30 percent of state prisons admits in 1950, 34 percent in 1960, roughly 40 percent in 1970, and 42 percent by 1980. (p. 83)

Private prison corporations aren't the only businesses that profit from the prison industrial complex according to the research. A 2013 article by Liliana Segura entitled "*With 2.3 Million People Incarcerated in the US, Prisons Are Big Business,*" highlights telecommunications giant Global Tel Link (GTL) as a company that directly benefits from the prison industrial complex. With respect to Global Tel Link, "GTL wins its contracts by offering a kickback—or "commission"—to the prison or jail systems it serves" (Segura, 2013). However, "these high kickbacks translate into higher phone rates for family members" (Segura, 2013). GTL reportedly made revenues of more than \$500 million charging families "up to \$1.13 per minute" for phone calls from loved ones who are incarcerated (Segura, 2013).

Essentially, the research reveals that there are a number of synergies working hand and hand to generate substantial profits from the prison industrial complex. In addition, minorities are generally overrepresented in private prisons giving credence to the larger discussion at hand.

Summary

The central question of this paper is as follows: Is the prison industrial complex a new form of modern day slavery that unjustly incarcerates African-Americans for cheap labor? This chapter explored the results of three sub-questions as a framework for answering the central question. The next chapter will give a detailed interpretation of this phenomenon, and explain how this study adds to the discussion.

Chapter 5: Summary and Discussion

Introduction

The central question of this paper serves as the framework in establishing a connection between slavery and the prison industrial complex. The research initially touched on the precursors of the prison industrial complex; followed by the racial elements. Finally, the paper examined the synergies that benefit from the prison industrial complex. This chapter will include a summary of how the research supported the qualitative analysis, and end by discussing the significance of the findings.

Statement of Problem

This paper will answer the central question: “Is the prison industrial complex a new form of modern day slavery that unjustly incarcerates African Americans for cheap labor?” To answer this question in an efficient manner, I have assembled three sub-questions: What were the precursors of the prison industrial complex? What are the racial elements within the prison industrial complex? Who benefits from the prison industrial complex?

Review of Methodology

As noted in Chapter 3, this study was qualitative in nature and utilized a descriptive case study approach. The descriptive case study method was used to describe the phenomenon of the prison industrial complex relative to slavery. A triangulation of data was collected in order to

answer the three sub-questions proposed that in turn were used to answer the central question at hand.

Summary of Results

This section will interpret the results of each sub question proposed in Chapter 4 to enable the reader to understand how these results answered the major question.

Summary of Sub-Question 1

- **What were the precursors of the prison industrial complex?**

The findings suggest that there were four precursors to the prison industrial complex: slavery, Jim Crow segregation, ghettos and hyper-ghettos (Wacquant, 2002, p. 41). Chapter four detailed each institution as it relates to the prison industrial complex.

Slavery was gradually established through America's legal system (Higginbotham, 1980, p 27). Even the U.S. Constitution, America's supreme law of the land, included three provisions that legally recognized slavery (U.S. Const. art. I, § 2, cl. 3; U.S. Const. art. IV, § 2, cl. 3; U.S. Const. art. I, § 9, cl. 1). This peculiar institution provided white Southerners with a plantation based system of un-free fixed labor through black bondage (Wacquant, 2002, p. 44-45). Slavery was principally an economy in and of itself leaving many Americans divided over the moral implications of this practice (Smith, 1998, p. 3). Slavery ultimately led to The American Civil War between the Northern Union and Southern Confederacy; culminating with the enactment of the 13th Amendment to the Constitution of the United States (Vorenberg, 2001, p.2). However, when slavery was abolished it nearly crippled the southern economy (Wacquant, 2002 p. 45-46). Still, the 13th Amendment provided states with the necessary power to expand its jurisdiction by allowing slavery or indentured servitude through criminal conviction (National Archives and Records Administration, 2010). Namely, this legal wording established Jim Crow segregation—

an institution that maintained elements of slavery such as racial discrimination, black codes, and convict leasing laws (Dickerson, 2003, p. 43; Browne, 2007, p. 43).

Through Jim Crow segregation, the plantation system of slavery remained intact. Principally, African-Americans were convicted of petty crimes and forced to work as leased sharecroppers under an agrarian and extractive system (Wacquant, 2002, p. 45; Dickerson, 2003, p. 43). With the Jim Crow institution firmly in place in the South, many blacks migrated en masse to the Northern part of the United States for better living and employment prospects. Nonetheless, housing segregation and employment discrimination relegated blacks to ghettos ridden with crime (Massey, 1993, p. 36-40). Under the institution of the ghetto blacks were free and mobile; yet, racial segregation bound blacks to menial work in a segmented industrial manufacturing market (Wacquant, 2002, p. 47). Although the U.S. later enacted laws that forbade discrimination, black isolation progressed under hyper-ghettos (p. 52). Hyper-ghettos are extremely impoverished crime ridden areas that are a pipeline to prison. Essentially, “black” became synonymous with “criminal” ultimately leading to mass incarceration under the new institution which is the prison industrial complex (p. 56).

Thus, the results of sub-question 1 answered the main question by explaining the connection between slavery, its successive institutions, and the prison industrial complex. Essentially, slavery was the progenitor of racial discrimination, bondage and exploited black labor, and each of its successive institutions maintained these elements. The findings suggest that slavery’s legacy is now sustained through the institution of the prison industrial complex.

Summary of Sub-Question 2

- **What are the racial elements within the prison industrial complex?**

The research explored the disproportionate treatment that African-Americans face with respect to the “War on Drugs” and its associated laws. In addition, the research touched on arrests, U.S Sentencing guidelines, and zero-tolerance school policies. The results indicate that the “War on Drugs and its associated laws—namely the Anti-Drug Abuse Act of 1986 and The Anti-Drug Abuse Act of 1988—are responsible for the mass incarceration of blacks (McCurdy and Vagins, 2006, p. i). The aforementioned laws created mandatory minimum sentences for various drugs, and although whites on average possess, use, and traffic drugs more than blacks, blacks are approximately 3 times more likely than whites to be arrested for drugs (McCurdy and Vagins 2006, p. I; Fellner 2009, p. 272). The research also revealed that blacks face tougher sentences than whites upon conviction for nonviolent drug offenses (Mustard 2001, p. 285). The U.S. has strict sentencing guidelines that were specifically designed to eliminate disparities in terms of race/ethnicity (p. 285). However, the findings suggest that departures from these guidelines produce approximately 55 percent of the black-white difference in sentencing (p. 285). Finally, the research touched on the school-to-prison pipeline noting that black children were more likely to be suspended, expelled, involved in in-school arrests, or referred to law enforcement than white students (Suspensionstories, n.d). Wald and Losen (2003) explained that the disparity between how black children are treated relative to white students is largely because of racial profiling in schools (p. 13). In addition, Skiba (2000) noted that there is no evidence that black children misbehave more than white children; yet, black children are often given harsher punishment than white children for relatively minor offenses (p. 12).

The results of sub-question 2 answered the main question by detailing how the prison industrial complex consists of numerous racial elements that specifically affect African-Americans. The findings affirmed that this disparity in treatment is not a coincidence, but purely a continuation of elements that originated with slavery.

Summary of Sub-Question 3

- **Who benefits from the prison industrial complex?**

Finally, the study examined the synergies that worked together to create the prison industrial complex. In addition, the study focused on how the prison industrial complex was created; the reason for doing so; and the profit model associated with the system. The findings indicate that budget deficits pushed politicians to pass legislation to contract out prisons to private organizations (Marion, 2009, p. 217). These private prison corporations rely on mass incarceration for profits and typically lobby politicians for harsher penalties for nonviolent offenses (p. 217). Moreover, private prison corporations promote policies that increase recidivism rates among inmates (p. 217). One such private prison corporation, Corrections Corporation of America (CCA), is a billion dollar entity that noted in its 2013 annual report that harsh drug and immigration laws keep the company in business (p.5). Two studies by the group “In the Public Interest,” found that private prison corporations use inmate occupancy quotas, annual contract increases, and political contributions to maintain their profits (2013, p. 5) (2014, p. 4-5). What’s more, a study by Petrella (2013) revealed that private prisons intentionally house inmates of color by using the health and age of an inmate as a proxy for race. His study found that older unhealthier inmates tend to be Non-Hispanic, white, while younger inmates are typically people of color. As a result, minorities—especially African-Americans—are more likely to be exploited by private prisons for cheap labor. Finally, the study focused on a powerful

corporation that directly benefits from the prison industrial complex, Global Tel Link. This telecommunications giant “reportedly made revenues of more than \$500 million charging families “up to \$1.13 per minute” for phone calls from loved ones who are incarcerated” (Segura, 2013).

Thus, the results of sub-question 3 answered the main question by reporting on the synergies that benefit from the prison industrial complex. In particular, the findings revealed that the prison industrial complex is principally an economic system that is similar to slavery in that it relies on the disproportionate treatment of African-Americans, and the exploitation of labor to create profits for outside entities.

Relationship of Research to the Field

Chapter 3 noted that the descriptive case study method would be used to describe the phenomenon of the prison industrial complex relative to slavery. Ideally, this study intended to explore a sensitive issue to not only verify existing theories, but to also gain a new perspective on this topic. The research supported this effort by synthesizing ideas from numerous scholars and organizations. The literature identified four root causes of the prison industrial complex: slavery, Jim Crow segregation, the ghetto, and hyper-ghettos (Wacquant 2002, p. 41). This paper established a correlation between each institution relative to the prison industrial complex; noting that racial discrimination, bondage, and coerced labor are persistent elements. The paper then considered the racial elements of the prison industrial complex to determine if it would yield comparable findings with respect to the four institutions that preceded it. Finally, the study reviewed relevant data concerning the economical approach to the prison industrial complex. It became evident that the prison industrial complex was more than just a system to lock up those that broke the law. Rather, it was revealed that the prison industrial complex is a system that

encompasses all of the ills of slavery, racial discrimination, and free and coerced labor. In essence, the research provided a framework to not only answer the central question, but to contribute to the larger discussion at hand.

Discussion of Results

The findings yielded significant results with respect to the prison industrial complex relative to slavery. Looking past the qualitative and quantitative data; the context is real-life people who have been disproportionately affected by discriminatory laws and practices. Is it a coincidence that this system impinges on the rights of those whose ancestors were slaves? Initially, the purpose of this study was simply to compare and contrast slavery with the prison industrial complex. However, the research revealed shocking trends—specifically racial discrimination, bondage, and coerced labor among the four institutions that preceded the prison industrial complex. The results facilitated the following interpretation: slavery was the progenitor, and its three successive institutions gradually led to today’s criminal justice system.

Since slavery was immoral and inhumane, the transition to criminal punishment via the 13th Amendment was necessary to justify the use of slave-like conditions. Thus, each successive institution retained elements of slavery—racial discrimination, bondage and coerced labor—albeit in a more subtle manner. Furthermore, it explains why today’s system is primarily comprised of blacks who largely committed nonviolent drug offenses. Consequently, politicians allowed certain synergies such as private prison corporations, and businesses to capitalize on this practice. From a moral perspective, one must question why a country would allow businesses to profit from mass incarceration and high recidivism rates. Is it because the leaders of America are also benefitting from the prison industrial complex? Indeed, politicians created a multi-billion dollar industry under the insidious nature of institutionalized racism. Given that the war on drugs

has largely contributed to the mass incarceration of African-Americans, this area of the law requires more attention.

I recommend that states and the federal government consider rehabilitative alternatives for nonviolent drug offenses. In addition, the federal government must reform zero-tolerance school policies, and review all deviations from U.S. Sentencing guidelines to reduce racial disparities. I believe these steps are necessary to right a wrong that originated with slavery.

Conclusion

This paper is guided by the central question: Is the prison industrial complex a new form of modern day slavery that unjustly incarcerates African-Americans for cheap labor? Three sub-questions were proposed as a framework to answer the central question at hand. The first sub-question revealed the root causes of the prison industrial complex and highlighted the connection to slavery. The second sub-question focused on the racial dynamics of the prison industrial complex; noting that African-Americans are disproportionately affected. Finally, the third sub-question explained the synergies that profit from the prison industrial complex. Given these points, the research answered the main question by noting the similarities between slavery and the prison industrial complex; thus establishing a connection. Essentially, during slavery the core of the economy was the plantation, the dominant social type was the slave, and the form of labor was un-free and fixed. Conversely, under the prison industrial complex the core of the economy is the prison, the dominant social type is the prisoner, and the form of labor is once again un-free and fixed. This connection explains the subtle and insidious way that the mass incarceration, particularly of African Americans, is a paradigm for the exploitation of black labor comparative to; nevertheless, different from slavery.

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